

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS
CORRESPONDING TO k_1 AND k_2

$\Delta H_1^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta E_1^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta E_2^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
25.42	25.74	23.48	2.20	2.44	-7.64

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Physicochemical and Catalytic Studies of some Molybdates†

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MOLYBDATES have been very popular as catalysts for oxidation and dehydrogenation reactions^{1,2}.

Though some of these have been used as catalysts in ammoxidation³, and a few others in the oxidation of methyl alcohol⁴, their effectiveness in the oxidation of CO has not been tested so far. In the present work, five molybdates have been investigated for their catalytic activities for CO oxidation and an attempt has been made to correlate the increasing order of activation energies with the labilisation of the double bonds.

Experimental

Molybdates of Cu, Co, Bi, Ni and Ag were prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of oxides, carbonates or nitrates of the above metals with ammonium molybdate, dissolving the mixture in concentrated nitric acid, evaporating the solution to dryness and calcining the intimate mixture at around 600° for 12 h.

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X-Ray diffraction patterns of the samples were taken in a Philips X-ray diffractometer. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

CO was produced by treating oxalic acid with concentrated H₂SO₄. It was passed through purifying towers and via a flow meter to a mixer. The purifying train consisted of towers containing pellets of sodium hydroxide and active charcoal powder, respectively. Air was fed from cylinders through the purifying towers to the mixer. The mixer was then passed through the catalyst bed in a reactor surrounded by a furnace. The collecting unit consisted of standard baryta solution. The CO₂ formed was estimated by the residual method.

Results and Discussion

The three most intense lines in the X-ray diffraction pattern of each of the molybdates as given in the ASTM powder diffraction file were observed in the patterns obtained in the present work also. The infrared spectra (1 000–600 cm⁻¹ range) the samples are given in Fig. 1.

X-Ray diffraction patterns show that molybdates have been formed completely in all the cases. Infrared spectral data (Table 1) show an interesting trend. For transition metal oxides the ir band due to the presence of metal oxygen double bond occurs around 1 000 cm⁻¹. For Mo—O double bond in MoO₃, the band occurs at 985 cm⁻¹. In these transition metal oxides, the most reactive oxygen atom is the one that is linked to the metal by a double bond. If the oxides containing a metal-oxygen double bond (e.g. MoO₃) is mixed with a second metal oxide, this ir band gets shifted to the lower frequency side⁵ due to labilisation of the double bond, i.e. weakening of the bond. The decreasing order of wave numbers corresponding $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ among the molybdates investigated is found to be MoO₃ > Co > Ni > Cu > Bi > Ag. Interestingly, the increasing order of activation energies is fairly the same as the above, Co < Ni < Cu < Bi < Ag. In general, a larger departure from the 985 cm⁻¹ value denotes a weaker Mo=O bond. However, this weakening of bond can have any perceptible effect on the catalytic behaviour of the substance only if the mechanism of oxidation involves lattice oxygen participation, i.e. participation of oxide in the oxidation. If on the other hand, the mechanism consists of adsorption of gaseous O₂ or CO, the labilisation of the metal-oxygen bond need not result in a decrease in activation energy⁶. In the present work, the increase in activation energy, E_a (Table 1) for CO oxidation parallels increase in ease of labilisation of M=O bond. Since the value of E_a for the reaction does not decrease with the weakening of the M=O bond, the lattice participation may be ruled out unlike the case of other reactions such as the oxidation of methanol by molybdates⁷. It is highly likely that CO interacts with Mo^{VI} rather than with the other metal ion in

Fig. 1. Ir spectra of samples : (○) Co-Mo, (■) Ni-Mo, (×) Cu-Mo, (●) Ag-Mo and (—) Bi-Mo.

TABLE 1—Mo=O IR BANDS OF THE SAMPLES AND ACTIVATION ENERGIES (E_a) FOR THE OXIDATION OF O
Flow rate=166 ml/min⁻¹

Sample	$\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ cm ⁻¹	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹
Silver molybdate	820	3.0
Cobalt molybdate	940	1.0
Nickel molybdate	940	1.0
Copper molybdate	850	2.6
Bismuth molybdate	840	2.6

the combination as the former is a better Lewis acid⁶.

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Study of the Effect of Storing Time on Oscillatory Reaction involving Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid

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OSCILLATORY chemical reaction involving several organic substrates has been the subject of investigation¹⁻⁵. It was observed in our study⁶ that acetone dicarboxylic acid drives the system oscillatory. It was further observed that the oxidation of citric acid by ceric salt produced acetone dicarboxylic acid (ADA) in aqueous solution (hereafter, solution A*) according to the equation,

Solution A* responded well⁶ in the oscillatory system when it replaced freshly prepared acetone dicarboxylic acid. The present communication reports the effect of storing the ingredients of solution A* to various lengths of time.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade (B.D.H). The stock solutions of 0.056 M citric acid and 0.1M Ce^{IV} sulphate were prepared in 1.5M sulphuric acid medium. Potassium bromate (Baker, A.R.) was dried at 120°. A 0.03M solution of KBrO₃ was prepared in 1.5 M sulphuric acid. The ingredients of solution A*, i.e. 0.056 M citric acid (10 ml) and

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